

Methylation of Phenol over Alumina in the Vapour Phase : Influence of Copper Sulphate

V. KRISHNASAMY*, T. V. SUBRAMANIAM and S. SOUNDARARAJAN

A. C. College of Technology, Anna University, Guindy, Madras-600 026

Manuscript received 17 March 1980, revised 21 January 1982, accepted 25 August 1982

Phenol is methylated using methanol over alumina and alumina impregnated with varying amounts of copper sulphate at 360, 400 and 440°, at a molar ratio of 0.75 : 1 of phenol to methanol. Over alumina, phenol undergoes direct nuclear (carbon) methylation, giving cresols and xylenols. Alumina with 10 and 20% copper sulphate catalyses both carbon and oxygen methylation forming cresols and anisole, respectively. Xylenols, which were absent over the above two catalysts, appear when the copper sulphate concentration increases to 30%. Further increase of copper sulphate from 30 to 40% not only enhances the proportion of xylenols in the products by increasing the temperature and the contact time, but also decreases that of anisole under these conditions. However, the concentration of cresols seems to be unaffected. Methylation of phenol follows a first order kinetics irrespective of the concentration of copper sulphate in the catalysts.

ALKYLATION is an important unit process widely employed in chemical industries for introducing alkyl groups into other substances notably in hydrocarbons and hydroxy compounds of the aromatic series. Among the alkylation reactions, methylation of phenol has got great industrial importance, as methyl phenols are largely used as chemical intermediates for the production of valuable industrial products. Most of the work done on methylation of phenol is patented¹⁻³. Consequently, very little information regarding these investigations is available. Others, who studied this reaction, used high acidic alumina⁴⁻⁶, zeolite⁷ and silica-alumina⁸, with a view to get more of *m*-cresol, probably on account of its importance as a raw material for perfumes. Kotanigawa⁹⁻¹¹ and co-workers investigated extensively the methylation of phenol using Fe₂O₃ catalyst impregnated with various metallic oxides and observed that Fe₂O₃-CuO was the most effective combination for selective methylation of phenol at the *ortho* position to get 2,6-xyleneol. It has been reported recently¹² that alumina doped with copper sulphate suppresses the formation of xylenols and the product composition consists of a mixture of anisole and cresols. In the present investigation, alumina-copper sulphate has been employed to study the methylation of phenol in detail and to obtain the kinetic parameters.

Experimental

Preparation of materials :

Alumina A : Alumina was prepared by hydrolysing aluminium isopropoxide (B.D.H., A.R.) with distilled water. The precipitated aluminium hydroxide was filtered, washed thoroughly, cut into cakes, dried at 120° for 24 hr and activated at 500° in a stream of dry air for another 24 hr. The activated samples were sieved (85-120 mesh) and a part

of it was mixed with 0.5% analytical grade stearic acid binder and made into cylindrical pellets of 0.5 cm diam and 4 mm height and the rest was used as support for copper sulphate.

Catalysts B, C, D and E were obtained by impregnating alumina A with appropriate amounts of copper sulphate (B.D.H., A.R.) solution in water to give respectively 10, 20, 30 and 40% by weight of copper sulphate. Catalysts B, C, D and E were made into pellets of the same size mentioned above. Prior to each run the catalyst was kept at 500° for 8 hr in an atmosphere of pure dry oxygen until no oxides of carbon was detected in the exit gas. After use, it was found that the copper sulphate remained unaffected.

Phenol used was of B.D.H., AnalaR grade and used as such. Methanol (B.D.H., L.R.) was purified further by fractionation. The purity of reactants was checked by gas chromatography.

Apparatus and procedure :

The reactions were carried out at atmospheric pressure in a fixed bed flow type reactor. The experimental set-up is shown in Fig. 1, which consists of (i) a constant flow bottle, (ii) preheater-vapourizer, (iii) a capillary flow meter for metering the feed, (iv) tubular reactor and (v) condenser and receiver.

The mixed feed was passed through a capillary tube flow meter which was calibrated earlier using the actual reactant mixtures. The feed enters the preheater-vapourizer (15 cm long and 1.2 cm internal diam) maintained at 220° through a micro feeder for conversion into vapour before entering the reactor. The catalyst (6.36 g) was kept in a Pyrex glass reactor tube (1.5 cm internal diam and 20 cm long). Pyrex glass beads (4 mm diam) were placed above the catalyst bed to a height of 3 cm. A vertical

Fig. 1. Experimental set-up.

thermowell is provided for inserting thermocouple to measure the temperature of the catalyst bed. The reaction products were passed through a condenser and collected in a receiver kept in ice. Both the preheater and the reactor were heated on the outside by a uniformly wound nichrome wire, whose length had been predetermined to give the requisite temperature. This was then lagged by means of asbestos cords and magnesia powder to prevent loss of heat. The energy input is controlled by a 8 A dimmerstat. The temperature of the catalyst bed is indicated by a Pt-Pt-Rh thermocouple connected to a temperature controller-cum-indicator.

The liquid products collected for the first 15 min of each run of 45 min duration were discarded, and the products collected after this period were analysed. This was done to ensure the attainment of steady state for the reaction over the catalyst, and also to eliminate temperature fluctuations, if any, due to the starting of the reaction. The catalyst was regenerated after the reaction. Runs were repeated to check the reproducibility of the results.

The liquid products of methylation of phenol were identified and estimated using a one meter

column of Apiezon-L in a gas chromatograph (Model NCL-AIMIL MK II B) with Flame Ionization Detector. The optimum condition for the best resolution within a reasonable time was found to be : column temperature 130°, FID temperature 225°, nitrogen inlet pressure of 15 psi with hydrogen as fuel.

For the identification of different peaks in a chromatogram, retention times for the different compounds were obtained by introducing pure substances. For quantitative estimation, synthetic mixtures containing the different compounds in varying known proportions were introduced and calibration curves relating the concentration with peak area were drawn¹⁸⁻¹⁵.

Results and Discussion

The thermodynamic feasibility of methylation of phenol to cresols had been ascertained by calculating the free energy change of the reaction by Van Krevelan's method using the equation,

$$F_T = A + BT$$

where A and B are constants of the equation. Using standard values¹⁶ for the constants A and B, the change in free energy for the reaction at 600, 650 and 700°K were calculated and the values are found to be -17.37, -17.33 and -17.07 kcal/mole, respectively, indicating that methylation of phenol is quite feasible within the temperature range given above. Three contact times, namely, 17.05, 23.44 and 37.50 hr were chosen by trial and error methods. The reactions were carried out at 360, 400 and 440° and the molar ratio of phenol to methanol was kept constant at 0.75 : 1 throughout the investigation. The above temperatures were chosen because the conversion was found to be low below 360° and the phenols may decompose to benzene, toluene and xylene above 440°.

Increase of both contact time (Table 1; Fig. 2) and temperature (Table 2; Fig. 3) enhances the conversion of phenol over each catalyst but the enhancement is found not to be linear. The concentration of alkyl phenols in the product increased

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF CONTACT TIME ON PRODUCT DISTRIBUTION IN MOLES AT 400°

Catalyst	Contact time in hr	Anisole formed	Cresol formed	Xylenol formed	Phenol unreacted
A	17.05	—	0.6290	0.1642	0.2128
	23.44	—	0.7414	0.1880	0.0706
	37.50	—	0.7263	0.1446	0.1291
B	17.05	0.4995	0.3715	—	0.1190
	23.44	0.5010	0.3800	—	0.1028
	37.50	0.4982	0.3990	—	0.0876
C	17.05	0.3211	0.5881	—	0.0890
	23.44	0.3210	0.5900	—	0.0697
	37.50	0.3185	0.6118	—	0.1600
D	17.05	0.2020	0.6380	—	0.1420
	23.44	0.2180	0.6400	—	0.0800
	37.50	0.2100	0.6580	0.0520	0.1275
E	17.05	0.0400	0.5823	0.2502	0.0887
	23.44	0.0458	0.5900	0.2760	0.0687
	37.50	0.0524	0.6100	0.2800	0.0676

Fig. 2. Effect of contact time on product distribution at 400° over catalyst E.

Fig. 3. Effect of temperature on product distribution at a contact time of 37.5 hr over catalyst E.

TABLE 2—EFFECT OF TEMPERATURE ON PRODUCT DISTRIBUTION IN MOLES AT CONTACT TIME 37.5 HR.

Catalyst	Temp. °C	Anisole formed	Cresol formed	Xylenol formed	Phenol unreacted
A	360	—	0.5264	0.0698	0.4038
	400	—	0.7263	0.1446	0.1291
	440	—	—	—	—
B	360	0.4523	0.3911	—	0.1566
	400	0.4983	0.3990	—	0.1028
	440	0.4012	0.4507	0.0520	0.0960
C	360	0.3018	0.5014	—	0.1968
	400	0.3185	0.6118	—	0.0697
	440	0.2612	0.6531	0.0580	0.0277
D	360	0.2016	0.6053	0.0488	0.1443
	400	0.2100	0.6580	0.0520	0.0800
	440	0.1200	0.7604	0.0985	0.0211
E	360	0.0821	0.5000	0.2099	0.1980
	400	0.0524	0.6100	0.2800	0.0576
	440	0.0256	0.6100	0.2800	0.0844

Fig. 4. Effect of copper sulphate on product distribution. Temp. 400°; contact time 37.5 hr.

over this catalyst may be attributed to either (i) direct nuclear methylation of phenol or (ii) rearrangement of anisole, that may be formed, by simultaneous parallel reactions as indicated in the reaction scheme. The complete absence of anisole in the product rules out its formation and subsequent rearrangement to alkyl phenols though this type of rearrangement was observed by Cullane and Chard¹⁷ over alumina. It may be concluded that over alumina, direct nuclear methylation of phenol occurs.

Impregnation of alumina with 10% copper sulphate (catalyst B) brings about the following changes in the activity pattern of the catalyst. Over this catalyst, anisole is formed to a maximum extent of 0.5 mole while the amount of cresols are reduced considerably with complete elimination of xylenols. The same type of products are formed over catalyst C and also over catalyst D except at high temperature and high contact time (*vide* Tables 1 and 2). In the case of catalyst E, a considerable proportion of xylenols is formed in addition to anisole and cresols.

Unlike over catalyst A, both oxygen and carbon methylations occur simultaneously over catalysts B

with increase of these two parameters over each catalyst while the proportion of anisole went down under these conditions. The effect of copper sulphate on the distribution of products depended mainly on its concentration in the catalyst (Tables 1 and 2; Fig. 4).

Over alumina (catalyst A), anisole was absent, cresols were formed to a maximum extent of 0.74 mole per mole of phenol reacted along with a sizable amount of xylenols. The absence of anisole

to E giving anisole and cresols as suggested in the scheme. With increase in reaction temperature, contact time and copper sulphate concentration in the catalyst, the anisole rearranges to cresols which are further methylated to xylenols, and as a result, C/O ratio increases. The rearrangement of anisole to cresol was confirmed by injecting anisole through catalyst E. The various possible transformations are given in the scheme.

tion consisting of anisole and cresols, they do not agree with the observation that copper sulphate suppresses the formation of xylenols. It may be emphasised that not only the proportion of xylenols in the product increases with increase in copper sulphate concentration, the anisole concentration is also reduced drastically (vide Tables 1 and 2).

Kinetics : The reaction sequence pertaining to the methylation of phenol, illustrated in the reaction scheme, shows that it involves parallel and consecutive steps simultaneously thereby making the process complex. On account of the complexity of the reaction, the kinetics of the reactant alone is followed by its disappearance with time. A plot of $-\ln(1-x)$, (where x is the mole of phenol reacted) vs contact time (i.e., W/F_{A_0} , where W is the weight of the catalyst and F_{A_0} is the flow rate of the reactant mixture/hr) for catalyst E shows a straight line relationship (Fig. 7) indicating that the methylation of phenol follows a first order kinetics. The

Fig. 5. Effect of copper sulphate on C/O ratio at three temperatures. Contact time 37.5 hr.

Fig. 6. Effect of copper sulphate on C/O ratio at three contact times. Temp. 400°C.

Though the observed data over alumina-copper sulphate agree partly with the report appearing in a chemical weekly¹² that copper sulphate when incorporated with alumina gives a product composi-

Fig. 7. First order plot for catalyst E.

TABLE 3—EFFECT OF TEMPERATURE ON C/O RATIO (CARBON METHYLATION / OXYGEN METHYLATION)				
Catalyst	Temp. °C	C/O ratio 17.05 hr	C/O ratio 23.44 hr	C/O ratio 37.50 hr
B	360	1.0060	0.9594	0.8649
	400	0.7498	0.7588	0.8010
	440	1.0800	1.1050	1.2528
C	360	1.6000	1.6440	1.6800
	400	1.8000	1.8980	1.9200
	440	2.6000	2.6000	2.7190
D	360	3.0500	2.9900	3.2440
	400	3.2700	3.2100	3.6900
	440	7.8400	10.2700	7.1560
E	360	5.6100	8.1500	8.7700
	400	20.5500	18.3100	16.4800
	440	56.0000	68.7600	34.7600

Fig. 8. Arrhenius plot for catalyst E.

Scheme 1

log of rate constants was plotted against the reciprocal of absolute temperature for catalyst E (Fig. 8). The activation energies, calculated from the slopes of the Arrhenius plots of all the catalysts, are shown in Table 4.

TABLE 4—EVALUATION OF REACTION RATE CONSTANTS

Catalyst	Rate constant k (hr^{-1})			Energy of activation kcal/mole
	k_{300}	k_{400}	k_{440}	
A	—	—	—	7.60
B	0.0095	0.0125	0.0180	7.20
C	0.0120	0.0170	0.0240	6.93
D	0.0160	0.0270	0.0340	6.60
E	0.0220	0.0340	0.0520	6.40

References

- OSCAR HINSBERG, *Ger. Patent*, 538, 376, Dec. 11, 1930; *Chem. Abs.*, 1932, 26, p. 1617.
- F. J. SOWA and G. F. HENNING, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 709.
- W. C. OFFUT, *U. S. Patent*, 2684989, July 20, 1954.
- L. F. ALBRIGHT and R. N. SHREVE, *Ind. Engg. Chem.*, 1956, 48, 1551.
- VEEHLING, GUNTER, HULTNER and RUDOLF (Union Rheinische Braunkohlen Kraftstoff A. G.) *Chem., Abs.*, 1969, 70, 37457a.
- R. NORRIS SHREVE, *Chem. Abs.*, 1968, 68, 59279e.
- Chem. Abs.*, 1966, 65, 2173c; [General Elec. Co. Neth., Appl. 6,506,830 (cl. c. 07c), Nov. 30 1965; U. S. Appl., May 29, 1964].
- Coal Tar Research Assoc. (by JOHN A. SHARP and RAYMOND E. DEAN); *Chem. Abs.*, 1967, 67, 32461a.
- T. KOTANIGAWA, M. YAMAMOTO, K. SHIMOKAWA and Y. YOSHIDA, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Japan*, 1971, 44, 1961.
- T. KOTANIGAWA and K. SHIMOKAWA, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Japan*, 1974, 47(b), 1535.
- T. KOTANIGAWA, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Japan*, 1974, 47, 2466.
- Annual Report 1975-76 of the Regional Research Laboratory, Hyderabad, *Chemical Weekly*, 1977, 23, 72.
- A. DERWEIRELDT, *J. Chromatography*, 1961, 5, 98.
- L. CANDAL-BOSCH, *J. Chem. Educ.*, 1964, 41, A235.
- PRESTON, "A Guide to Analysis of Phenols", Poly. Science Corporation.
- R. C. REID and T. K. SHERWOOD, "Properties of Liquids and Gases", McGraw-Hill, New York, 1958.
- N. M. CULLINANE and S. J. CHARD, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1945, 821.